

Expanding SafeSU capabilities by leveraging security frameworks for contention monitoring in complex SoCs

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ABSTRACT

The increased performance requirements of applications running on safety-critical systems have led to the use of complex platforms with several CPUs, GPUs, and AI accelerators. However, higher platform and system complexity challenge performance verification and validation since timing interference across tasks occurs in unobvious ways, hence defeating attempts to optimize application consolidation informedly during design phases and validating that mutual interference across tasks is within bounds during test phases.

In that respect, the SafeSU has been proposed to extend inter-task interference monitoring capabilities in simple systems. However, modern mixed-criticality systems are complex, with multilayered interconnects, shared caches, and hardware accelerators. To that end, this paper proposes a non-intrusive add-on approach for monitoring interference across tasks in multilayer heterogeneous systems implemented by leveraging existing security frameworks and the SafeSU infrastructure.

The feasibility of the proposed approach has been validated in an RTL RISC-V-based multicore SoC with support for AI hardware acceleration. Our results show that our approach can safely track contention and properly break down contention cycles across the different sources of interference, hence guiding optimization and validation processes.

1. Introduction

With the advent of new applications in the safety-critical system's domain requiring increased performance capabilities, the utilization of complex System-On-Chips (SoCs), including multicores and hardware accelerators, becomes a real necessity. Unfortunately, these complex SoC platforms increase the difficulty of the already stringent verification and validation steps required in safety-related products. Timing (performance) verification is one of the steps that is jeopardized when integrating several computing elements sharing a non-negligible amount of resources, since task execution time is significantly affected by the interference (i.e., contention) created in the shared resources by co-running tasks.

Existing approaches to deal with contention in multicores either advocate for eliminating the contention using strict scheduling approaches (e.g., time-division multiplexing) or rely on utilizing usage quotas to control – instead of eliminating – the amount of contention a particular task can experience. In this paper, we follow the latter approach (contention monitoring and enforcement) and propose an end-to-end contention monitoring and control mechanism that, by

introducing non-intrusive hardware support, allows to effectively limit the execution time inflation that a particular task experiences in a modern heterogeneous SoC.

To enable precise contention tracking, our mechanism relies on having a consistent view of the SoC requests initiators across the different shared resources and the interconnect architecture, as security frameworks like Sifive's Woldguard [1] provide. In this context, our contention monitoring mechanism leverages the existing interconnect request information provided by the given security frameworks to track the contention not only at the shared networks but also at the endpoints of our SoC (e.g., shared caches) without the need to modify them.

This work builds on top of the SafeSU (Safe Statistics Unit) module [2] to monitor interconnect activity, extending it to support more complex SoCs with caches and multilayer interconnects, enabling both endpoint and interconnect contention monitoring. By doing so, our mechanism facilitates the safe consolidation of low/moderate-criticality performance-hungry tasks, like Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS) functions using hardware accelerators, with critical tasks such as braking and steering systems.

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In particular, this paper makes the following contributions:

- We propose a new non-intrusive mechanism that leverages existing security approaches to accurately monitor contention (end-point and interconnect) across SoC platforms with multi-layered interconnects.
- We extend SafeSU's multicore interconnect contention monitoring to incorporate endpoint contention in a non-intrusive manner.
- We realize an implementation of our mechanism in an RTL 6-core RISC-V multicore testbed that includes convolutional network accelerators and CPUs in a hierarchical interconnect architecture.
- We thoroughly validate the mechanisms and evaluate the results of our implementation with home-built resource-stressing kernels to represent the worst possible contention situations.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the background on mixed-criticality systems and contention monitoring in real-time systems. Section 3 presents our multilayer network-based contention monitoring approach. Section 4 provides an implementation of the approach described in Section 3. Section 5 presents the contention results provided by our proposed approach. Section 6 reviews some related work, and Section 7 summarizes the conclusions derived from the results presented in this paper.

2. Background

Critical real-time embedded systems must follow a development process dictated by domain-specific safety standards such as ISO26262 [3] in the automotive industry. Safety standards define different integrity levels spanning from no safety requirements (e.g., Quality Managed or QM in automotive) to varying safety requirements, such as Automotive Safety Integrity Level (ASIL)-A to ASIL-D, where ASIL-D items have the most stringent safety requirements.

Verification, validation, and safety measures required increase with the integrity level of the item being certified or qualified. Since items with varying integrity (or criticality) levels may need to be integrated into the same system for efficiency reasons, the design must ensure that low criticality tasks cannot propagate misbehavior to high criticality ones to avoid mixed-criticality related risks [4].

Functional and timing interference must be considered in mixed-criticality systems. Memory Protection Units (MPUs) and Memory Management Units (MMUs) are usually deployed, along with appropriate hypervisors, to provide some form of partitioning and, hence, avoid functional interference. However, efficient sharing of resources (e.g., not full partitioning) may lead to timing interference. In particular, standards explicitly impose the need for freedom from interference using ISO26262 terminology, as a means to ensure that tasks meet their safety requirements, such as completing execution by specific deadlines.

Mixed criticality systems are systems where tasks of different criticality can coexist. When unique resources whose utilization by a single task is below 100% are shared, the overall system becomes more efficient in Size, Weight, and Power (SWaP) since we increase the utilization of resources already in place [5].

However, sharing resources such as caches, buses, and interconnects leads to an increase in the latency of individual requests because they have to wait for the previous requests to finish (serialization), causing interference on the shared cache lines (state change), which ultimately challenges freedom from interference [6].

This interference can be estimated at the task or system level. However, estimates must be conservative for safety reasons, ultimately leading to underutilization of computing resources. In a heterogeneous system with several CPUs and AI accelerators, where casuistics to be considered are massive, the potential for execution time inflation is immense. Thus, there has been a push to develop mechanisms that can either track the execution time inflation that the task experiences

Fig. 1. SafeSU architecture and connections.

due to other tasks running in the system [7–10] or efficiently share resources [11–13].

While we need strategies to control time interference for safety purposes (including mixed-criticality systems), it can be challenging when interference arises simultaneously in various locations within the SoC. Existing mechanisms estimate contention either via transaction counting, throttling, or cache usage. Transaction counting and throttling approaches fail to accurately capture the contention that a transaction causes on each subsystem, as they only work by limiting the primary bus pressure, failing to consider a heterogeneous system with multiple-layer interconnects.

On the other hand, cache monitoring approaches fail to consider contention beyond cache accesses. For example, in a heterogeneous system with GPUs or AI accelerators not connected to the CPU cache, those accelerators and GPUs can cause huge interference that would be difficult to quantify with existing approaches. Therefore, mechanisms scaling to the challenge of high-performance multilayer heterogeneous SoCs become increasingly needed.

3. SafeSU

The SafeSU (Safe Statistics Unit) is a pioneering system utility specifically designed to address the complexities of managing and mitigating multicore timing interference in Systems-on-Chip (SoCs). With the increasing deployment of multicore architectures in safety-critical and high-performance computing environments, the need for precise control and observability of inter-core interactions has never been more crucial. The SafeSU integrates several monitoring and control components to offer insights into the system's state, ensuring both the reliability and efficiency of multicore SoCs. As Fig. 1 presents, the baseline SafeSU is able to monitor inter-core interference in the AHB bus for the presented system.

3.1. Safesu core components

The SafeSU comprises three primary components, each tailored to fulfill specific roles within the multicore architecture:

- Request Duration Counter (RDC): This component monitors the duration of various event types in CPU clock cycles, enabling accurate tracking of interconnect usage and event timing.
- Cycle Contention Stack (CCS): The CCS provides detailed data on how each core's activities affect the overall system performance. By recording the number of cycles a core's requests are stalled by others, the CCS aids in identifying bottlenecks and optimizing task scheduling to minimize contention and maximize throughput.
- Maximum-Contention Control Unit (MCCU): Allocating and enforcing multicore timing interference quotas, the MCCU plays a pivotal role in maintaining system stability. It ensures that no core exceeds its allocated share of system resources, thereby preventing performance degradation from excessive contention.

Fig. 2. Shared bus contention with CCS signal.

This paper focuses on extending the SafeSU capabilities to enable more precise and safe contention monitoring in complex SoCs.

3.2. Contention tracking, the CCS concept

The SafeSU proposes using the concept of Contention Cycle Stack (CCS) [14] to track the contention on the system. The CCS concept is illustrated in Fig. 2, where “Contention” represents the CCS signal of contention core 1 over core 0. On cycle 2, core 0 requests access to the bus, but this access is denied as core 1 has the bus and needs to end its transaction. Therefore, on cycle 2, there was one contention cycle from core 1 to core 0. This contention cycle is represented and latched in cycle 3 rising edge. The same occurs in cycles 6 and 7, where the core 0 request is not granted. Thus, these two requests that should have taken 2 cycles to complete have now taken 5 cycles to complete due to contention. This 3-cycle difference is represented via our contention signal.

There is a CCS signal for each event that the system monitors. Therefore, extending contention monitoring to other shared resources is as simple as creating a CCS generator for that specific hardware module. We chose the CCS signaling schema for our system since it easily allows extending monitoring capabilities to different SoC architectures.

3.3. Use cases

The integration of the SafeSU into a system provides observability and controllability of multicore timing interference, which is instrumental in several ways:

- **Enhanced Debugging and Optimization:** System designers can leverage the detailed metrics provided by SafeSU to refine their designs, leading to optimized resource allocation and improved overall system performance.
- **Reliability in Real-time Operations:** By actively monitoring and adjusting to the system’s state, SafeSU ensures operational reliability, which is crucial for systems deployed in environments where failure can lead to significant consequences.
- **Safety and Compliance:** For applications requiring stringent adherence to safety standards, such as automotive and aerospace systems, SafeSU ensures that the system operates within safe limits, thereby aiding compliance with industry regulations.

4. Contention monitoring in multilayer heterogeneous SoCs

The objective of this work is to design a mechanism that enables contention monitoring in large complex SoCs in a non-intrusive manner. That is, we target a mechanism that can be instantiated and interfaced in complex existing SoCs, enabling deriving safe contention bounds without requiring modifications in all the involved hardware modules.

The proposed mechanism provides metrics that allow the user to identify the cause of each cycle of contention similarly to Fig. 3(b). This figure illustrates how the proposed mechanism can capture the execution time inflation that the task under analysis (gray segment)

Fig. 3. Example of a system with contention monitoring.

experiences from each other actor on the system (pink and orange segments). Fig. 3(a) represents the system where the execution time of Fig. 3(b) is obtained. The system representation illustrates how the contention unit is instantiated as a plug&play unit and monitors contention across the entire interconnect and at both the LLC and Memory controller, only observing traffic on the network.

4.1. Contention monitoring approach

This work builds on top of the hypothesis that, while not all contention occurs in the interconnect, all interconnect and endpoint contention can be accurately measured and inferred at the interconnect level.

We define ACD (Actual Contention Delay) as the additional delay request experienced due to contention on shared resources. The upper bound of the ACD is known in the literature as WCD (Worst Contention Delay) [15].

Our mechanism aims to capture the ACD time and source each initiator experiences due to sharing resources in the system. An initiator is an entity in our system that initiates transactions, also usually referred to as a master in interconnect standards like AXI (Advanced eXtensible Interface) or AHB (Advanced High-performance Bus). Note that we exclude sources of interference caused by alterations in the internal state of the shared resources (e.g., cache evictions) since those are not observable at the interconnect level. To avoid such sources of interference, we rely on well-known techniques like cache coloring and way partitioning for caches or memory bank partitioning for memory controllers [16].

The goal of our mechanism is to measure the ACD falling into these two categories:

- **ACD due to interconnect contention:** The ACD produced in the network due to arbitration or transfer delays that would otherwise not happen if the task was executed alone.
- **ACD due to endpoint contention:** The ACD is produced in a network endpoint (i.e., LLC and Memory controller) but measured in the interconnect by considering endpoint behavior.

With these objectives, this work extends the baseline SafeSU contention monitoring capabilities to monitor endpoint and total contention across multiple network layers. To flatten network hierarchy and implement a unified initiator naming scheme, we propose leveraging existing security frameworks. This way, we extend the SafeSU capabilities to more complex systems and provide contention estimates considering end-point contention.

Fig. 4. Representation of contention measurement mechanism.

4.2. Measuring contention at the interconnect

The SafeSU [2] approach is taken to measure interconnect contention. This approach dictates that when the bus is occupied and a given initiator requests access to the bus, the contention is assigned to the initiator owning the interconnect. This type of contention is illustrated as arbiter contention in Fig. 4 and it is the only contention measurement that the baseline SafeSU supports. One of the contributions of this work is extending the baseline mechanism by adding monitoring support to the contention that occurs at endpoints (such as the LLC and Memory controller). This endpoint contention is often not a direct consequence of interconnect activity (as buses can be idle while the endpoint is not accepting requests).

For that purpose, we introduce endpoint initiator tracking support in the form of queues as represented in purple in Fig. 4. These queues aim to track contention at endpoints by monitoring the control signals of each endpoint and keeping track of request precedence. They assume some serialization inside the endpoint and leverage the assumption to assign contention to the head of the FIFO from the elements at the tail of the FIFO. This contention is represented as HoL (Head of Line) contention Fig. 4 and will be referred to as endpoint contention in this paper. The granularity at which endpoint serialization is assumed depends on the particular implementation and the capabilities of the interconnect and the endpoint to handle multiple outstanding requests.

4.3. Leveraging security frameworks for safety

In multilayered SoCs, transaction ownership might be obscured by the bridging between layers. However, existing security frameworks like SiFive Worldguard [1], ARM TrustZone [17], and AMD MPAM [18] attach domain information to each SoC transaction, propagating this information across the whole SoC.

In particular, Trustzone [19] proposes two *worlds* intertwined in the processor logic and used to increase the system's security. It propagates world information by appending one bit to the address of these requests to represent the request's world, essentially separating addresses of different worlds.

Worldguard [1] is a similar security approach proposed by SiFive for the RISC-V architecture. Worldguard implements transaction ownership and world propagation across the interconnect to protect the I/O and memories. It does so by attaching world information to each request on the SoC. Notice, though, that these security mechanisms do not target the timing interference problem.

In this paper, we leverage this domain information provided by the aforementioned security frameworks for contention monitoring, thus using them as a common interface for safety and security. In particular, we propose taking advantage of the Worldguard naming scheme to

assign a world ID to each CPU of the system, thus alleviating the problem of request ownership dilution when crossing several interconnect layers.

The request ownership dilution problem makes the true request initiator to be obscured by network bridges, making the network bridges the visible initiator in the lower network and, thus, losing information about the real source of the request. An example of this obscuring bridge is a shared cache, where requests access the cache with a core as an initiator and leave the cache to the main memory with the cache as the initiator. This makes contention accounting after the shared cache harder, as the source is now diluted due to the bridging between layers.

5. End-to-End implementation on the target system

We have implemented the proposed contention monitoring approach in a multicore RISC-V based SoC that comprises six CPUs with private L1 caches, a shared Last Level Cache (LLC), and an AI inference accelerator.

5.1. Baseline SoC

The SoC uses Frontgrade Gaisler NOEL-V processor and its components and builds an architecture similar to the GR7xV [20] processor for next-generation Space Systems. The NOEL-V processor is an industrial in-order dual-issue RISC-V processor implementing the RV64GCH architecture. The SoC has an AI inference initiator that accesses memory using the AXI4 network. The SoC test system is open source,¹ making the reuse of the results of this paper possible for the reader. The test system is as presented in Fig. 3(a).

5.2. Request tracking: The unified ID mechanism

As the baseline SoC used in this paper does not have any security framework support yet, we implemented a Worldguard-like approach as it provides enough granularity.

We selected four bits to propagate world information, thus providing 16 different worlds. Indeed, as our system did not previously use the AXI4 QoS field (with a width of four bits), we leverage this unused field to propagate world information, thus easing implementation.²

As we have 16 worlds available on the target system, we decided to use a light aggregation of initiators into worlds. The implemented initiator-to-world mapping on the proposed system consists of mapping each core to a world (6 worlds) and grouping all convolution accesses to a new world. This way, the system uses seven different world IDs. To implement this world assignment at each initiator in our system, we devise a simple register that sets that initiator's world. This register can only be accessed by the safest world.

Propagating initiator information through the L2 cache

For bridging AHB and AXI4, simple bridges relay world information from each complementary field, and complex bridges, like the LLC, rely on slightly more complex propagation mechanisms. In the LLC, evicted lines get the world of the evictor independently of their initiator. This eliminates the need to store initiator information on each cache line and is sufficient for tracking contention across worlds.

This mechanism is shown in Fig. 5, where an initiator replaces the data in way 0 with world 1. Even though the data was set by ID 0, the transaction that causes the eviction of the data on way 0 is marked with ID 1 (the initiator that creates the eviction). This approach is used as it allows us to keep track of contention across cache accesses without the overhead of storing the source ID bits on the cache. Moreover, for statically partitioned caches, this approach works identically to storing the owner of each cache line in the cache.

¹ <https://gitlab.com/selene-riscv-platform/selene-hardware>

² World and ID are used interchangeably in this article, as each transaction's world is stored on each bus's QoS field.

Fig. 5. Standard world propagation mechanism for LLC.

5.3. Contention monitoring

The test system presented in Fig. 3(a) uses AHB as a first-level interconnect and AXI as a second-level interconnect. As they are very different network specifications, contention monitoring needs are different for both, and they are described individually in Sections 5.3.1 and 5.3.2.

5.3.1. Contention tracking on the AHB bus

We implemented a CCS generator for the AHB and AXI4 buses to track the contention generated by different initiators. Generating AHB network contention signals is implemented as follows.

The CCS output from each aggressor over a victim is as presented on Fig. 2, where core 1 is the aggressor and core 0 the victim. As the AHB bus can only serve a request at a time, there can only exist contention caused from one aggressor to multiple victims. This is the only type of contention supported by the baseline SafeSU.

One of the main additions over the baseline SafeSU in the contention monitoring aspect is the possibility of supporting endpoint contention not directly visible on the bus. In the case of the target system, this indirect contention monitoring support is used to track all LLC contention fully.

To implement AHB endpoint contention, the proposed approach is to build a CCS generator that triggers a CCS signal when the bus is granted to a new initiator, but the endpoint is not ready to take in a new request. This CCS generator then assigns contention from the previous initiator that made a transaction on the bus to the current initiator blocked on the bus.

5.3.2. Contention tracking on the AXI bus

The AXI4 CCS generator aims to track the contention that requests experience on the AXI4 bus and the potential AXI4 endpoints, such as the memory controller, through the AXI4 bus. Although AXI4 request contention can be due to arbitration at the shared crossbar or memory controller, we found that the memory controller constitutes most of the contention.

The developed generic AXI4 endpoint contention monitor is deployed in the target system to monitor contention occurring in the memory controller of the target system. The presented AXI4 contention monitor supports the following sources of contention:

1. Read to Read contention. Contention to the requests in the tail of the read queue from the head of the read queue.
2. Write to Write contention. The same mechanism as to the above but latching writes.
3. Read arbitration to read contention. Read contention to the requests requesting to access the endpoint from the read request being processed currently in the endpoint.
4. Write arbitration to read contention. The same mechanism as the above but for write arbitration.
5. Read arbitration to write contention. If the endpoint is not accepting reads and is not currently processing a read, we assume that the write being processed is at fault and blame it for read contention.
6. Write arbitration to read contention. The same mechanism as the above but for write arbitration.

The proposed endpoint contention monitor uses the initiator propagation mechanism to identify the real source of the contention. The proposed monitor assumes response serialization from the tracked target to simplify implementation and reduce monitor area. Indeed, most targets respond to requests in the order they are performed. In this particular setup, the Xilinx MIG memory controller [21] on the target system serializes requests, as evidenced by the tight estimates the implemented contention monitor presents in the results section. However, the tracked resource must be analyzed previously to monitor instantiation, as the AXI4 standard also supports having out-of-order responses.

5.3.3. Contention monitoring unit

The SafeSU (Safe Statistics Unit) processes the CCS signals from the AHB and AXI4 CCS generators. This unit provides statistics for the CCS signals, making the tally of contention generated by each initiator to another initiator easily software-accessible. It further enables controlling the maximum contention that an initiator creates to another initiator via hardware interrupt signaling or hardware stalling of the offending cores. For instance, a trigger is defined for several input signals and a threshold, and once the threshold is reached, it raises a hardware interrupt, stalling the offending initiator.

The SafeSU was initially able to provide limited support for endpoint monitoring (when requests were blocked). However, with the improvements proposed in this paper, the SafeSU is now able to monitor endpoint contention fully and to track the contention in multi-layer networks.

6. Experimental validation

6.1. Methodology and setup

We have prototyped the SoC described in Section 5 using a Xilinx VCU118 FPGA board running at 100 MHz. Fig. 3(a) provides a high-level representation of the target SoC. The SoC comprises 6 Gaisler NOEL-V dual-issue in-order cores with a private L1 cache connected to a shared AHB bus. That same AHB bus is the front end of the shared L2 cache. The L1 cache is write-through, so all write and uncached read accesses will be written through the shared AHB bus to the L2 cache. The L2 cache has an AXI4 backend interconnected with an AXI4 crossbar. The AXI4 crossbar has one more initiator, an AI inference accelerator. The AXI4 crossbar has one target, the Xilinx DDR4 MIG memory controller.

The results presented are obtained using the implemented system on the Xilinx VCU118 board. The software runs on bare metal mode for more controllability in the experiments.

6.2. Stressing microkernels

For the CPU initiators, we use stressing microkernels that can generate contention on the different shared buses, L1 cache misses with L2 cache hits to stress the AHB bus, and L2 cache misses to stress both the AHB and AXI bus. We first run each microkernel on a single CPU core to calculate the execution time in isolation from the task. Then, we run the task with contenders to analyze whether the mechanism adequately estimates contention. In particular, we use the following resource-stressing microkernels.

- *ld_l1hit*: Creates load hits on the private l1d cache. It does not stress shared resources, as each core's l1d cache is private.
- *st_l1hit*: Creates store hits on the private l1 cache. This l1d cache is write-through, thus creating pressure on the shared AHB bus to the rest of the cores.
- *ld_l2hit*: Creates load capacity misses on the private l1 cache and hits on the shared l2 cache.
- *st_l2hit*: Creates store hits on the shared L2 cache.

Fig. 6. Effect of endpoint monitoring on contention. Only CPU traffic.

- *st_l2miss*: Creates store misses on the shared L2 cache.
- *ld_l2miss*: Creates load misses on the shared L2 cache.

All previously presented micro-kernels use cache-coloring to avoid undesired inter-process cache evictions, as contention due to cache evictions is not visible at the interconnect level and must be controlled with other means (e.g., partitioning).

The test system also comprises a convolutional neural network accelerator used in this work to create heavy traffic in the AXI interconnect and memory controller endpoint. The workload running on such AI accelerator is a dummy neural network inference.

6.3. Contention measurement results

This section will test the proposed approach with the presented stressing kernels in CPU-only and heterogeneous system configurations.

The “R” metric is presented to evaluate the proposed mechanism. This metric represents the ratio between execution time in isolation plus measured contention and the execution time of the task when running with contenders. It illustrates the accuracy of our contention measuring mechanism. The “R” metric is expressed as :

$$R_j = \frac{EX_{iso} + \sum_{i=1}^{N_{src}-1} contention_i^j}{EX_{multicore}} \quad (1)$$

EX stands for Execution time. The closer the *R* metric is to one, the more precise the measurement is. However, underestimating contention (i.e., $R < 1$) must be avoided since it means the actual execution time of the critical task is not upper-bounded by the contention measurements as required to preserve the temporal integrity of the system. Thus, the closer the “R” metric to 1 without going below it, the better the contention measurement.

In this section, all results are obtained by executing the stressing microkernels in all cores and observing the contention of those kernels over core 0. In some cases, the convolutional accelerator creates traffic in the AXI4 network, while in some cases, we study inter-core interference purely.

6.3.1. Inter-core contention measurement

Figs. 6 and 7 are bar plots that present the average and standard deviation of 5 runs of the presented benchmarks. As observed in such figures, the deviation between runs is small, as such workloads are running in bare metal mode, making the casuistic limited.

Fig. 6 presents the contention-measurement improvements of the proposed mechanism over the baseline SafeSU where all cores are contending for accessing the shared LLC. That is the improvement of the new approach over the baseline mechanism due to the addition of endpoint monitoring. Fig. 6 shows that the proposed approach improves

over the baseline in all cases where the baseline SafeSU produced unsafe estimates ($R < 1$). However, some few cases still fail to provide tight *R* estimates. Specifically, store misses create significant contention overestimation on both baseline and proposed approaches. The contention measurements overestimate these microbenchmark combinations due to some accesses from the processor being non-blocking but being counted towards contention. In particular, our mechanism cannot differentiate between dirty and non-dirty evictions, needing to count all L2 evictions as dirty to preserve system safety.

6.3.2. Heterogeneous SoC contention measurement

Fig. 7 presents the results of the *R* metric with the monitored CPU executing the victim stressing kernel, all the aggressor CPUs executing the aggressor kernel, and the convolutional accelerator creating heavy network traffic on the AXI4 LLC backend and memory controller. This figure presents similar results when the core under analysis hits the LLC, as the convolutional accelerator creates contention after the LLC, thus having a limited impact.

Fig. 7 with the baseline mechanism depicts severe contention underestimation when the task under analysis misses in the LLC. However, with the approach proposed in this paper, there is no contention underestimation in any case, thus proving the soundness of the proposed endpoint contention measurements, unified contention metrics, and initiator propagation presented in this paper.

Fig. 8 presents the results of *victim = ld_l2miss* in Fig. 7 in cycles instead of using the *R* metric. This representation is chosen to showcase the improvements proposed in this paper and the fine-grained contention measurements that the improved SafeSU manages.

In Fig. 8, the blue cross represents the Execution time in multicore of the task under analysis, while the Isolation bar represents the Execution time in isolation of the task, and the rest of the stacked bars represent the contention from different sources as measured by the proposed mechanism. As noted in the previous explanation, those variables are used to obtain the *R* metric as presented in Eq. (1).

Fig. 8 showcases the contention impact each initiator creates on all the networks as presented to the system via the SafeSU metrics. These metrics help monitor the correct behavior of the different tasks of the system and take corrective action in case of detecting a misbehaving task.

According to Fig. 8, the baseline SafeSU as presented in [2] severely underestimates ACD for a heterogeneous system because it lacks the features presented in this paper. Fig. 8 in *baseline+endpoint* showcases that when endpoint contention monitoring is added to the baseline SafeSU, it does not underestimate contention. However, it severely overestimates contention when crossing network boundaries, as it lacks the initiator propagation capabilities proposed in this paper, thus needing to consider all contention coming from the victim’s network as

Fig. 7. Effect of endpoint monitoring on contention. Only CPU traffic. CPU plus convolutional accelerator traffic.

Fig. 8. Contention monitoring capabilities introduced in this paper. Victim: ld_12miss with Convolutional accelerator.

Table 1

FPGA hardware resource utilization of the proposed method.

FPGA resource	Full system	Only mechanism	Overhead
LUT	493 459	8121	1.6%
Registers	356 410	3155	0.9%
Carry8	11 842	346	2.9%

victim-generated traffic. This is highlighted with the last column of Fig. 8, where, when source propagation is added to the SafeSU, it provides safe and accurate estimates of the contention and execution time of the system’s tasks.

6.4. Hardware overhead

The proposed approach is a plug&play mechanism that can be applied to any existing SoC in a non-intrusive manner since no IP modifications are needed if a security framework like Worldguard is implemented. We also implemented this mechanism using industrial interfaces such as AXI4 and AHB to ease integration. Implementing the mechanism in other bus technologies is also possible but has not been covered in this work.

We have analyzed the SoC area resources of our FPGA implementation to measure the hardware overhead. Detailed hardware overheads are shown in Table 1, where the needed synthesized FPGA resources are laid out. As we can see, our mechanism incurs a very low hardware overhead. Most of the hardware overhead comes from the SafeSU contention monitoring capabilities, and a small part of the overhead comes from the CCS generators needed to monitor interconnect activity.

7. Related work

The traditional approach to control the contention is to use TDM (Time Division Multiplexing) on shared networks such as [22–25]. TDM aims to eliminate the contention on a system and increase the predictability by giving each initiator time slots to transmit interference-free on the network. This makes the interference predictable. However, it reduces the system’s maximum throughput due to actors not fully utilizing their time slots, and unlike our approach, it requires completely re-designing the system interconnect.

Some other works aim for interference control based on rate-limiting requests. These works work under the assumption that lowering shared resource pressure from the contenders will cause the victim to have a predictable execution time inflation ceiling. One of these works is the BRU [8] or Bandwidth Regulation Unit. The BRU is a hardware mechanism that controls the amount of interference that resources can create to each other by rate-limiting the interfering resources. Similarly, as in our work, AXI-REALM [26] covers the contention control in AXI interconnects. However, they also rely on limiting the bandwidth of requests to limit the contention they can cause. Thus, it inherits the same limitations of other rate-limiting or budget-based mechanisms.

However, Memory bandwidth and priority partitioning approaches such as [8,11,26] fail to address the non-uniformly distributed memory access patterns of modern software [27] as several programs can be run at the same time while preserving timing when their memory-bound sections are not concurrent. The bandwidth regulation approaches previously mentioned force all system tasks to artificially lower memory bandwidths to conform to the worst possible case, creating an inefficient system. Memguard [12] manages to capture this case, creating a

more efficient system. However, it falls under another drawback of rate-limiting: multilayered bandwidth-based rate-limiting produces many cases that are hard to monitor. For instance, a system where bandwidth is regulated before a shared LLC might encounter few accesses, causing a large contention due to the caches, and a system that is bandwidth-regulated after the LLC might encounter cases with limited contention in the memory but large contention in the accesses to the LLC. Thus, necessitating a mechanism to unify all contention metrics such as the one proposed in this work.

More advanced specifications exist that can lead to time-predictable behavior, such as the recent ARM MPAM specification [18], which defines IDs that can be attached to different system processes. Those IDs can be used to regulate a process or a group of processes' memory bandwidth with different granularities, they can also be used to assign minimum and maximum bandwidths and cache partitioning and regulation schemes. As for similarities with this paper, the MPAM specification priority partitioning and bandwidth partitioning can be used to enforce certain predictability [13].

Our work builds on top of existing proposals such as the SafeSU [2] and MCCU [7] that enable contention monitoring and enforcement in on-chip buses. The rationale behind these approaches is not to regulate the access to shared resources but to account for the contention resulting from those accesses. Thus, this approach can lead to a much more efficient system than memory bandwidth and priority partitioning as it does not limit per-core throughput prematurely, it only does so informedly. We then extend the SafeSU and MCCU approaches by adding extended endpoint contention monitoring support and implementing an End-to-End contention interconnect-based monitoring approach in complex heterogeneous SoCs. Additionally, by implementing a transaction ownership mechanism compatible with existing approaches for security, we minimize the overheads and modifications required in existing SoCs to implement our solution, which, in turn, eases the adoption of our proposed mechanism.

8. Conclusions

In this paper, we propose a non-intrusive contention monitoring approach that enables monitoring the contention that every resource on a heterogeneous SoC generates to any other system resource. We evaluate the proposed solution on a heterogeneous RISC-V SoC architecture prototyped on an FPGA using resource-stressing kernels to validate the effectiveness of the proposed approach.

The results show that the proposed transaction tracking and contention monitoring approach is a highly efficient and accurate framework that synergizes well with current security approaches, providing safety guarantees to regular SoCs in a non-intrusive manner. This approach can be easily integrated into complex SoCs to provide accurate, fast, and trustworthy execution time inflation measurements with low hardware overhead, helping end users validate that timing behavior meets the established requirements.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Pablo Andreu: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Sergi Alcaide:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **Pedro Lopez:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Jaume Abella:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **Carles Hernandez:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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References

- [1] G. Di Natale, F. Regazzoni, V. Albanese, F. Lhermet, Y. Loisel, A. Sensaoui, S. Pagliarini, Latest trends in hardware security and privacy, in: 2020 IEEE International Symposium on Defect and Fault Tolerance in VLSI and Nanotechnology Systems, DFT, 2020, pp. 1–4, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/DFT50435.2020.9250816>.
- [2] G. Cabo, F. Bas, R. Lorenzo, D. Trilla, S. Alcaide, M. Moretó, C. Hernández, J. Abella, SafeSU: an extended statistics unit for multicore timing interference, in: 2021 IEEE European Test Symposium, ETS, 2021, pp. 1–4, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/ETS50041.2021.9465444>.
- [3] ISO, ISO 26262 - road vehicles functional safety, 2018, <https://www.iso.org/standard/68383.html>.
- [4] R. Ernst, M. Di Natale, Mixed criticality systems—a history of misconceptions? IEEE Des. Test 33 (5) (2016) 65–74, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/MDAT.2016.2594790>.
- [5] A. Burns, R.I. Davis, A survey of research into mixed criticality systems, ACM Comput. Surv. 50 (6) (2017) <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/3131347>.
- [6] M. Chisholm, B.C. Ward, N. Kim, J.H. Anderson, Cache sharing and isolation tradeoffs in multicore mixed-criticality systems, in: 2015 IEEE Real-Time Systems Symposium, 2015, pp. 305–316, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/RTSS.2015.36>.
- [7] J. Cardona, C. Hernandez, J. Abella, F.J. Cazorla, Maximum-contention control unit (MCCU): Resource access count and contention time enforcement, in: 2019 Design, Automation & Test in Europe Conference & Exhibition, DATE, 2019, pp. 710–715, <http://dx.doi.org/10.23919/DATE.2019.8715155>.
- [8] F. Farshchi, Q. Huang, H. Yun, BRU: Bandwidth regulation unit for real-time multicore processors, in: 2020 IEEE Real-Time and Embedded Technology and Applications Symposium, RTAS, 2020, pp. 364–375, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/RTAS48715.2020.00011>.
- [9] K. Du Bois, S. Eyerhan, L. Eeckhout, Per-thread cycle accounting in multicore processors, ACM Trans. Archit. Code Optim. 9 (4) (2013) <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/2400682.2400688>.
- [10] L. Subramanian, V. Seshadri, A. Ghosh, S. Khan, O. Mutlu, The application slowdown model: Quantifying and controlling the impact of inter-application interference at shared caches and main memory, in: 2015 48th Annual IEEE/ACM International Symposium on Microarchitecture, MICRO, 2015, pp. 62–75, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/2830772.2830803>.
- [11] D.R. Hower, H.W. Cain, C.A. Waldspurger, PABST: Proportionally allocated bandwidth at the source and target, in: 2017 IEEE International Symposium on High Performance Computer Architecture, HPCA, 2017, pp. 505–516, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/HPCA.2017.33>.
- [12] H. Yun, G. Yao, R. Pellizzoni, M. Caccamo, L. Sha, MemGuard: Memory bandwidth reservation system for efficient performance isolation in multicore platforms, in: 2013 IEEE 19th Real-Time and Embedded Technology and Applications Symposium, RTAS, 2013, pp. 55–64, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/RTAS.2013.6531079>.
- [13] M. Zini, D. Casini, A. Biondi, Analyzing arm's MPAM from the perspective of time predictability, IEEE Trans. Comput. 72 (1) (2023) 168–182, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/TC.2022.3202720>.
- [14] J. Jalle, M. Fernandez, J. Abella, J. Andersson, M. Patte, L. Fossati, M. Zulianello, F.J. Cazorla, Contention-aware performance monitoring counter support for real-time mpocs, in: 2016 11th IEEE Symposium on Industrial Embedded Systems, SIES, 2016, pp. 1–10, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/SIES.2016.7509440>.
- [15] M. Panic, C. Hernandez, E. Quinones, J. Abella, F.J. Cazorla, Modeling high-performance wormhole NoCs for critical real-time embedded systems, in: 2016 IEEE Real-Time and Embedded Technology and Applications Symposium, RTAS, 2016, pp. 1–12, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/RTAS.2016.7461342>.
- [16] S.W. Cheng, J.J. Chen, J. Reineke, T.W. Kuo, Memory bank partitioning for fixed-priority tasks in a multi-core system, in: 2017 IEEE Real-Time Systems Symposium, RTSS, 2017, pp. 209–219, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/RTSS.2017.00027>.

- [17] B. Ngabonziza, D. Martin, A. Bailey, H. Cho, S. Martin, TrustZone explained: Architectural features and use cases, in: 2016 IEEE 2nd International Conference on Collaboration and Internet Computing, CIC, 2016, pp. 445–451, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/CIC.2016.065>.
- [18] ARM, Arm® Architecture Reference Manual Supplement, ARM, 2022.
- [19] S. Pinto, N. Santos, Demystifying arm TrustZone: A comprehensive survey, ACM Comput. Surv. 51 (6) (2019) <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/3291047>.
- [20] CAES, GR740, GR765 and GR7xV: SPARC and RISC-V for on-board computing, 2022, The RISC-V in Space workshop. <http://microelectronics.esa.int/riscv/rvws2022/index.php>. (Accessed 5 June 2023).
- [21] AMD Xilinx, UltraScale Architecture-Based FPGAs Memory IP v1.4, AMD Xilinx, 2022.
- [22] M. Schoeberl, S. Abbaspour, B. Akesson, N. Audsley, R. Capasso, J. Garside, K. Goossens, S. Goossens, S. Hansen, R. Heckmann, S. Hepp, B. Huber, A. Jordan, E. Kasapaki, J. Knoop, Y. Li, D. Prokesch, W. Puffitsch, P. Puschner, A. Rocha, C. Silva, J. Sparsø, A. Tocchi, T-CREST: Time-predictable multi-core architecture for embedded systems, J. Syst. Archit. 61 (9) (2015) 449–471, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.sysarc.2015.04.002>, URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1383762115000193>.
- [23] K. Goossens, J. Dielissen, A. Radulescu, AEthernet network on chip: concepts, architectures, and implementations, IEEE Des. Test Comput. 22 (5) (2005) 414–421, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/MDT.2005.99>.
- [24] M. Schoeberl, F. Brandner, J. Sparsø, E. Kasapaki, A statically scheduled time-division-multiplexed network-on-chip for real-time systems, in: 2012 IEEE/ACM Sixth International Symposium on Networks-on-Chip, 2012, pp. 152–160, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/NOCS.2012.25>.
- [25] T. Picornell, J. Flich, C. Hernández, J. Duato, Enforcing predictability of many-cores with DCFNoC, IEEE Trans. Comput. 70 (2) (2021) 270–283, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/TC.2020.2987797>.
- [26] T. Benz, A. Ottaviano, R. Balas, A. Garofalo, F. Restuccia, A. Biondi, L. Benini, AXI-REALM: A lightweight and modular interconnect extension for traffic regulation and monitoring of heterogeneous real-time SoCs, 2023, [arXiv:2311.09662](https://arxiv.org/abs/2311.09662).
- [27] H. Yun, W. Ali, S. Gondi, S. Biswas, BWLOCK: A dynamic memory access control framework for soft real-time applications on multicore platforms, IEEE Trans. Comput. 66 (7) (2017) 1247–1252, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/TC.2016.2640961>.

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